

Novel bioactive flavonol glycoside from *Desmodium gangeticum* DC.[†]

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A novel bioactive flavonol glycoside, m.p. 279–281°; C₂₈H₃₂O₁₅, [M]⁺ 608 (FABMS) has been isolated from the methanol soluble fraction of the stems of *Desmodium gangeticum* and its structure has been characterised as 3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy-8-methyl flavone-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 6)-O- β -D-galactopyranoside by various colour reactions, chemical degradations and spectral analysis. The compound **1** showed antimicrobial activity against various bacteria and fungi.

Desmodium gangeticum DC.^{1–3} belongs to family Leguminosae which is known as 'Sarivan' in Hindi. It is found almost throughout in India, ascending to 5000 ft. in Himalayas. The plant is considered to be antipyretic and anticatarrhalic. Its root is hot and bitter and useful in the treatment of chronic fevers, nausea, vomiting, cough and snake bite. Its seeds are used as febrifuge. We have reported the isolation and characterisation of a new flavone glycoside from the leaves of this plant⁴. In the present paper we report the isolation and identification of a novel bioactive flavonol glycoside, 3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy-8-methyl flavone-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 6)-O- β -D-galactopyranoside from the stems of this plant.

Results and discussion

The methanol fraction of stems of the plant afforded a novel bioactive compound **1**, m.p. 279–281°, C₂₈H₃₂O₁₅, [M]⁺ 608 (FABMS). It responded Molisch and Shinoda tests⁵ showing its flavonoidal glycosidic nature. It was crystallised as a yellowish needles compound. Its IR spectrum showed absorption bands at 3420 (-OH), 2945 (C-H), 1635 (>C=O), 1620 (aromatic ring system) and 1520, 1205, 860 cm⁻¹. Its UV spectrum with various shift reagents suggested the presence of free hydroxyl groups at C-5, C-7 and C-4' positions^{6,7}.

The compound **1** on acid hydrolysis with 10% H₂SO₄ yielded an aglycone **2**, m.p. 285–286°, C₁₆H₁₂O₆, [M]⁺ 300 (EIMS) and sugar moieties, identified as D-galactose and L-rhamnose. A retro-Diels-Alder fragmentation patterns resulted in the formation of ions at *m/z* 272, 271, 167, 166, 138, 134, 133. These results supported the presence of a methyl group and two hydroxyl groups in ring A and one hydroxyl group in ring B.

When aglycone **2** was treated with Ac₂O/pyridine it formed tetra acetyl derivative, **4**, m.p. 186–187°, C₂₄H₂₀O₁₀, and [M]⁺ 468 (EIMS). The ¹H NMR spectrum of **4** showed two *ortho* coupled doublets at δ 7.78 (2H, *J* 8.5 Hz), 6.98 (2H, *J* 8.5 Hz) corresponding for H-2',6' and H-3',5' respectively, confirming ring B to be symmetrically substituted. A singlet of one proton intensity at δ 6.34 was assigned to C-6 position. A singlet at δ 2.12 integrating for three protons was assigned to methyl group at C-8 position. Resonance signals at δ 2.34 (3H, s, 5-OAc), 2.38 (3H, s, 3-OAc), 2.84 (3H, s, 7-OAc) and 2.41 (3H, s, 4'-OAc) were indicative of four hydroxyl groups in aglycone **2**. The compound **2** was further identified as 3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy-8-methyl flavone with reported literature^{8,9}.

The compound **1** was treated with Ac₂O/pyridine at 120° for about 12 h and gave nona acetyl derivative **3**, m.p. 183–184°, C₄₆H₅₀O₂₄ and [M]⁺ 986. The ¹H NMR of **3** showed signals for anomeric protons at δ 5.74 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, H-1'') and 4.36 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, H-1'''), assigned to D-galactose and L-rhamnose respectively. A complex signal at δ 1.18 was assigned to rhamnosyl methyl group.

Permethylation¹⁰ of **1** followed by acid hydrolysis gave permethylated aglycone, identified as 3-hydroxy-5,7,4'-trimethoxy-8-methyl flavone which confirmed that -OH group at C-3 position of the aglycone was involved in glycosylation. The methylated sugar which were identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose and 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose according to Petek¹¹ showed that the C-1''' of L-rhamnose was linked with C-6'' of D-galactose and C-1'' of D-galactose was attached with C-3 position of the aglycone and also showed the interlinkage (1 \rightarrow 6) between the sugars.

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji.

1 R = α -L-Rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 6)-O- β -D-galactopyranoside

2 R = H

Enzymatic hydrolysis of the compound **1** by takadiastase liberated L-rhamnose and 3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy-8-methyl flavone-3-O- β -D-galactopyranoside as proaglycone which confirmed the presence of α -linkage between L-rhamnose and D-galactose. The proaglycone on further hydrolysis with almond emulsin yielded D-galactose and aglycone, confirming β -linkage between D-galactose and aglycone.

On the basis of the above evidences, the structure of a novel compound **1** was identified as 3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy-8-methyl flavone-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 6)-O- β -D-galactopyranoside.

The antimicrobial activity of the compound **1** was tested at its various dilutions using methanol as solvent against various bacteria and fungi and showed significant activity.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. UV spectra were determined in MeOH and IR spectra recorded in KBr discs. ^1H NMR spectra were run at 300 MHz using TMS as internal standard and CDCl_3 as solvent. ^{13}C NMR spectra were measured at 90 MHz using $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ as solvent.

Plant material : The stems of *Desmodium gangeticum* were collected around the Sagar region and taxonomically authenticated by Department of Botany, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar (M.P.), India. The herbarium specimen number 203 has been deposited in Department of Chemistry of this university.

Extraction and isolation : The air dried and powdered stems (3.5 kg) of the plant were extracted with 95% EtOH in a Soxhlet extractor. The total ethanolic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. The concentrated ethanolic extract was successively partitioned with petroleum ether (60–80 $^\circ$), benzene, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol. The methanol fraction of ethanolic extract of the plant was concentrated to brownish viscous mass, which was subjected to TLC examination using CHCl_3 : MeOH :

H_2O (15 : 9 : 4) as eluent and I_2 vapours as visualising agent, gave two spots, indicating it to be mixture of two compounds **1** and **1a** which were separated by TLC and purified by column chromatography over Si-gel G. The quantity of compound **1a** was found in very small amount therefore it was not possible to examine it further. Compound **1** was further purified by column chromatography which was found to be homogeneous on TLC examination. It was crystallised from methanol as yellowish needles compound (1.05 g). It had m.p. 279–281 $^\circ$; $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_{15}$, $[\text{M}]^+$ 608 (FABMS) (Found : C, 55.26; H, 5.25. Calcd. : C, 55.24; H, 5.29%). IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3420, 2945, 2935, 1635, 1620, 1520, 1205, 860 cm^{-1} ; UV λ_{max} (MeOH) 274, 331, 379; (+NaOMe) 262, 285, 427, (+NaOAc) 272, 329, 417; (+ AlCl_3) 268, 365, 379; (+ AlCl_3/HCl) 270, 365, 404; (+NaOAc/ H_3BO_3) 271, 326, 412 nm. It formed a nona acetyl derivative **3**, m.p. 183–184 $^\circ$, $\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_{24}$, $[\text{M}^+]$ 986 (Found : C, 55.95; H 5.09. Calcd. : C, 55.98; H 5.07%). ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 6.98 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-3', 5'), 7.78 (2H, d, J 8.5 Hz, H-2', 6'), 2.34 (3H, s, 5-OAc), 6.80 (1H, s, H-6), 2.85 (3H, s, 7-OAc), 2.12 (3H, s, 8-Me), 2.41 (3H, s, 4'-OAc), 5.74 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, H-1''), 2.92 (3H, s, 2''-OAc), 2.95 (3H, s, 3''-OAc), 2.98 (3H, s, 4''-OAc), 3.82–4.31 (6H, m, protons of galactose unit), 4.36 (1H, d, J 7.6 Hz, H-1'''), 2.80 (3H, s, 2'''-OAc), 2.14 (3H, s, 3'''-OAc), 2.20 (3H, s, 4'''-OAc), 1.18 (3H, m, Me-6'''), 4.75–5.35 (4H, m, protons of rhamnose unit). ^{13}C NMR (90 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) see Table 1. $[\text{M}]^+$ 608, m/z 462 (aglycone ion), 272, 271, 167, 166, 138, 134, 133.

Acid hydrolysis of compound 1 : Compound **1** was

Table 1. ^{13}C NMR (90 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) of compound **1**

Atom	δ -Value	Atom	δ -Value
C-2	148.3	C-5'	115.7
C-3	133.4	C-6'	129.4
C-4	176.6	C-1''	102.9
C-5	159.1	C-2''	71.4
C-6	98.4	C-3''	73.2
C-7	161.2	C-4''	68.1
C-8	104.3	C-5''	73.8
C-9	152.8	C-6''	65.7
C-10	104.6	C-1'''	101.2
C-1'	122.9	C-2'''	70.3
C-2'	129.7	C-3'''	70.6
C-3'	115.8	C-4'''	72.1
C-4'	159.2	C-5'''	58.3
		C-6'''	17.9

hydrolysed by refluxing with 10% H₂SO₄ for 6 h at 100°. On cooling, the aglycone **2** was crystallised from MeOH as yellowish plates which was identified as 3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy-8-methyl flavone, C₁₆H₁₂O₆, m.p. 286–287°, [M]⁺ 300 (EIMS), *m/z* 272, 271, 167, 166, 138, 134, 133 (Found : C, 64.03; H, 4.0. Calcd. : C, 64.01; H 4.02%); UV λ_{max} (+MeOH) 276, 332, 380; (+NaOMe) 265, 284, 428; (+AlCl₃) 269, 366, 434; (+AlCl₃/HCl) 268, 362, 405; (+NaOAc) 273, 330, 418; (+NaOAc/H₃BO₃) 273, 328, 411 nm; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) of **4** at δ 2.12 (3H, s, 8-Me), 6.80 (1H, s, H-6), 7.78 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 6.98 (2H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 2.38 (3H, s, 3-OAc), 2.34 (3H, s, 5-OAc), 2.85 (3H, s, 7-OAc), 2.41 (3H, s, 4'-OAc).

The aqueous hydrolysate was neutralised with BaCO₃ and BaSO₄ filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated and subjected to PC examination on Whatman filter paper No. 1 using *n*-BuOH : HOAc : H₂O (4 : 1 : 5, v/v) as solvent and aniline hydrogen phthalate as detecting agent yielded D-galactose (*R_f* 0.15) and L-rhamnose (*R_f* 0.36).

Permethylation and hydrolysis of the compound 1 : Compound **1** (15 mg) was treated with CH₃I (2 ml) and Ag₂O (20 mg) in DMF (5 ml) at room temperature for 2 days. The contents were filtered and the residue was treated with EtOH (3 ml). The syrupy residue was hydrolysed with 10% H₂SO₄ for 6–7 h. After usual work up, it yielded methylated aglycone, identified as 3-hydroxy-5,7,4'-trimethoxy-8-methyl flavone and methylated sugars, were identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose and 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-

galactose.

Antimicrobial activity of the compound **1** :

The antimicrobial activity of the compound **1** was tested at its various dilutions using methanol as solvent.

The antimicrobial activity was determined by Filter Paper Discs Diffusion (6 mm) method¹². The various bacterial species were first incubated at 45° for 48 h. The sterile filter paper discs (6 mm) were soaked with standard antibacterial agent and various test samples and were dried at 50°. The discs were then placed on soft nutrient agar (2%) petri plates previously seeded with suspension of each bacterial species. The diameters of zone of inhibition were measured at 37 ± 1° after 24 h. For fungal, Sabouraud's broth media¹³ with 4% agar was used for the preparation of plates and inoculated with spore and mycelium suspension of fungi obtained from 8 days old culture. The diameters of zone of inhibition were recorded at 27 ± 1° after 48 h. The various results are recorded in Table 2.

The results reported in Table 2 reveals that the antibacterial activity of the compound **1** showed more activity against gram positive bacteria viz. *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and was found to retain its activity even at dilution of 1 : 20. Compound **1** also exhibited good activity against fungal species viz. *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium oxysporum* even on very dilute concentrations. The investigations thus revealed that compound **1** may potentially be used as therapeutic agent diseases caused by these micro organisms.

Table 2. Antibacterial and antifungal activity of compound **1**

Sl. no.	Bacterial species	Diameters of zone of inhibition (mm)*					Std.**
		Compd. 1	1 : 5	1 : 10	1 : 15	1 : 20	
1.	(+) <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	19.5	17.0	10.0	10.5	6.5	19.5
2.	(-) <i>Escherichia coli</i>	13.5	10.5	8.5	7.0	6.5	17.4
3.	(-) <i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	14.5	9.5	5.5	2.5	–	18.5
4.	(+) <i>Bacillus coagulans</i>	17.5	14.5	11.5	10.0	9.8	21.0
5.	(-) <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	9.5	6.5	3.5	1.5	6.5	22.2
	Fungal species						Std.***
1.	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	11.5	9.5	7.5	6.5	6.0	14.5
2.	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	12.5	8.5	4.5	20.0	–	16.5
3.	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	15.5	12.5	10.5	10.0	9.5	21.0
4.	<i>Trichoderma viride</i>	12.5	9.5	5.5	3.5	–	23.0

*The diameters of zone of inhibition taken as average of four determinations in four different directions. **Streptomycin used as standard antibacterial agent. ***Griseofulvin used as standard antifungal agent.

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References

1. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R. Publication, New Delhi, 1996, p. 94.
2. K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", 2nd ed., Lalit Mohan Basu and Co., Allahabad, 1945, 1, 758.
3. "The Wealth of India, A Dictionary of Raw Materials and Industrial Products", C.S.I.R. Publication, New Delhi, 1952, III, 41.
4. R. N. Yadava and K. I. S. Reddy, *J. Inst. Chem.*, 1998, 70, 213.
5. J. Shinoda, *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1928, 48, 214.
6. T. J. Mabry, K. R. Markham and M. B. Thomas, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoids", Springer, New York, 1970, pp. 138-298.
7. D. K. Bhardwaj, A. K. Gupta, R. K. Jain and G. C. Sharma, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1981, 44, 656.
8. M. Mizuno, M. Linuma, T. Tanaka, N. Sakakibara, H. Murata and F. A. Lang, *Phytochemistry*, 1990, 29, 1277.
9. M. Linuma, M. Ohyama, T. Tanaka, M. Mizuno and F. A. Lang, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1991, 54, 1144.
10. S. Hakomoni, *J. Biochem.*, 1964, 66, 205.
11. F. Petek, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1965, 263.
12. C. Jasper, J. C. Maruzzella and P. A. Henry, *J. Am. Pharm. Asso.*, 1958, 471.
13. J. C. Vincent and H. W. Vincent, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1944, 55.